

REGULATORY PRIORITIZATION AND CATEGORIZATION OF ENDOCRINE DISRUPTING CHEMICALS

Option model considering substances from different regulations

Professor Dr. Bernd Schäfer

A. Specifying endocrine disruptors

A.1 WHO/IPCS definition

A.2 Definition of adversity

A.3 Available data under different regulations

A.4 Concepts for the identification of human health related ED properties

B. Assessment of human health related ED properties

B.1 Option 1: Biocides and plant protection products

B.2 Option 2: Chemicals under REACH

B.3 Option 3: Food additives

B.4 Option 4: Chemicals in plastic materials with food contact

B.5 Option 5: Ingredients in cosmetics

DEFINITION OF „ENDOCRINE DISRUPTORS“

WHO/IPCS 2002 definition

An Endocrine Disruptor is

- an exogenous substance or mixture
- that alters function(s) of the endocrine system
- and consequently causes **adverse health effects**
- in an intact organism, or its progeny, or (sub) populations.

in-vitro or in-vivo methods

in-vivo methods

Definition of “adversity” (WHO/IPCS 2004)

“A change

- in morphology, physiology, growth, reproduction, development or lifespan of an organism
- which results in impairment of functional capacity
- or impairment of capacity to compensate for additional stress or increased susceptibility to the harmful effects of other environmental influences.”

AVAILABLE DATA UNDER DIFFERENT REGULATIONS

Plant Protection Products (EG 1107/2009)	Biocides (98/8/EC; 528/2012)	Food additives (EG 1333/2008)	REACH (EG 1907/2006)	Plastics with food contact (EU 10/2011)	Cosmetics (EG 1223/2009)	Toys (2009/48/EC)	Clothing	others
Data set:								
✓	✓	(✓)	(✓)	(✓)				
		depending on production volume	depending on migration from material	depending on intended use			usually no product specific toxicological data	
Regulation:								
Approval procedure	Approval procedure (EU lists of approved additives: All/III)	Registration, Authorization	Risk assessment + authorization (EU list of authorized substances)	Risk assessment + addition to lists of • prohibited substances (All) • substances with restrictions (AIII) • allowed substances (AIV, V, VI)			Lists of substances that shall not be used (e.g. fragrances) or migration limits (some elements)	
			non-regulated substances	non-regulated substances	non-regulated substances		non-regulated substances	
				Reference to CLP and REACH			Reference to CLP and REACH	

For certain products specific regulations are in force with differences in intensity of regulation.

IDENTIFICATION OF HUMAN HEALTH RELATED ED PROPERTIES

I. Data evaluation (relevant endpoints)

II. Data analysis

II.1 Adverse effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies?

II.2 Do the available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?

II.3. Analysis of relevance for humans (default assumption: relevance)

III. Priorization/Categorization

Regulatory decision

A. Specifying endocrine disruptors

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B.1 Option 1: Biocides and plant protection products

B.2 Option 2: Chemicals under REACH

B.3 Option 3: Food additives

B.4 Option 4: Chemicals in plastic materials with food contact

B.5 Option 5: Ingredients in cosmetics

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- Are the adverse toxicological effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD CF Level 4/5)?
- The available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?
- Are the effects judged to be relevant to humans?

III. Categorization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED 1

No approval

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- regulation according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

ED CLASSES WITH RELEVANCE TO REGULATION*

Decision matrix	ED 1	ED 2
Guidance values for specific target organ toxicity after repeated exposure (STOT Repeated Dose Category 1, CLP)	exceeded	not exceeded
Severity of effect(s)	severe	not severe
Reversibility of effect(s)	(i)rreversible	reversible
Other aspects	(if applicable)	(if applicable)

* based on WHO/IPCS definition (2002)

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I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- Are the adverse toxicological effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD CF Level 4/5)?
- The available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?
- Are the effects judged to be relevant to humans?

III. Prioritization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED 1

SVHC identification (Article 57f)

- considered as to be of equivalent concern to CMR 1A/1B substances
Candidate for inclusion in REACH Annex XIV (Authorization)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- regulation according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

OPTION 2b: IDENTIFICATION OF EDs UNDER REGULATION (EC) NO 1907/2006

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- acceptable *in-vitro* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 1/2)
- Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 4/5)

Prioritization impossible!

III. Prioritization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED effect suspected

Substance Evaluation (Article 46)

- registrant(s) requested to provide further information

SVHC identification (Article 57f)

- considered as to be of equivalent concern to CMR 1A/1B substances
Candidate for inclusion in REACH Annex XIV (Authorization)

ED 1

Standard Risk Assessment

- regulation according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

ED 2

A. Specifying endocrine disruptors

- A.1 WHO/IPCS definition
- A.2 Definition of adversity
- A.3 Available data under different regulations
- A.4 Concepts for the identification of human health related ED properties

B. Assessment of human health related ED properties

- B.1 Option 1: Biocides and plant protection products
- B.2 Option 2: Chemicals under REACH
- B.3 Option 3: Food additives
- B.4 Option 4: Chemicals in plastic materials with food contact
- B.5 Option 5: Ingredients in cosmetics

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- Are the adverse toxicological effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD CF Level 4/5)?
- The available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?
- Are the effects judged to be relevant to humans?

III. Prioritization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED 1

No inclusion into

- Annex I (food additives approved for use in foods and conditions of use)
- Annex II (food additives approved for use in food additives, food enzymes and food flavourings, and their conditions of use)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- regulation according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

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EU No 10/2011 (Plastic materials and articles intended to come into contacts with food)

Article 5 (Union list of authorised substances)

Only the substances included in the Union list of authorised substances (Union list) set out in Annex I may be intentionally used in the manufacture of plastic layers in plastic materials and articles.

The Union list shall contain:

- (a) monomers or other starting substances;
- (b) additives excluding colorants;
- (c) polymer production aids excluding solvents;
- (d) macromolecules obtained from microbial fermentation

Article 11 (Specific migration limits)

Plastic materials and articles shall not transfer their constituents to foods in quantities exceeding the specific migration limits (SML) set out in Annex I.

Those specific migration limits (SML) are expressed in mg of substance per kg of food (mg/kg).

For substances for which no specific migration limit or other restrictions are provided in Annex I, a generic specific migration limit of 60 mg/kg shall apply.

acc. to EFSA (2008) Note for Guidance (Food Contact Materials);
EU No 10/2011 (Plastic materials and articles intended to come into contacts with food)

A. Migration < 0.05 mg/kg of food:

- Quantification of migration
- Genotoxicity assays:
 - * bacterial assay (Ames test)
 - * mammalian gene mutation assay
 - * chromosome aberration assay

B. Migration 0.05 – 5 mg/kg of food:

in addition to (A)

- 90d toxicity study (oral)
- investigation of bioaccumulation

C. Migration 5-60 mg/kg LM:

in addition to (B):

- Toxicokinetics and metabolism
- Chronic toxicity and carcinogenicity
- Developmental toxicity
- Reproductive toxicity

Problems:

- **Substances with low migration (< 0.05 mg/kg):** effects on the endocrine system are not addressed
suitable *in-vitro* studies addressing endocrine effects (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 1/2) should be mandatory for substances also with low migration!
- **substances with medium migration (< 5 mg/kg):** only very limited information on endocrine effects might come from the data set
- **substances with migration > 5 mg/kg:** endocrine effects are not directly addressed but could be uncovered from the data set in most cases

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- Are the adverse toxicological effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD CF Level 4/5)?
- The available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?
- Are the effects judged to be relevant to humans?

III. Prioritization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED 1

No inclusion into

- Annex I (Union list of authorised substances of regulation (EC) NO 10/2011)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- restrictions set according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

OPTION 4b: IDENTIFICATION OF EDCS UNDER REGULATION (EC) NO 10/2011

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties, available toxicological data from standardized or non-standardized tests, Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- **ED-related *in-silico* predictions, *in-vitro* assays and 90d toxicity study (oral) addressing ED toxicological endpoints should be mandatory!**

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- 90d toxicity study (oral) addressing ED toxicological endpoints
- acceptable *in-vitro* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 2)
- Read across, *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- Exposure

III. Priorization

Possibility for prioritization depends on quality of data!

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED effect suspected

Request for further toxicity testing

- applicant(s) requested to provide further information

ED 1

No inclusion into

- Annex I (Union list of authorised substances of regulation (EC) NO 10/2011)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- restrictions set according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

OPTION 4c: IDENTIFICATION OF EDCS UNDER REGULATION (EC) NO 10/2011

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties, available toxicological data from standardized or non-standardized tests, Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- ED-related *in-silico* predictions and a basic set of *in-vitro* assays addressing ED endpoint should be mandatory!

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- acceptable *in-vitro* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 1/2)
- Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 4/5)

Priorization impossible!

III. Priorization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED effect suspected

Request for further toxicity testing

- applicant(s) requested to provide further information

ED 1

No inclusion into

- Annex I (Union list of authorised substances of regulation (EC) NO 10/2011)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- restrictions set according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

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Article 18 of Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009

the placing on the market of cosmetic products shall be prohibited where, in order to meet the requirements of this Regulation,

- the final formulation
- ingredients or combinations of ingredients

has been the *subject of animal testing* using a method other than an alternative method after such alternative method has been validated and adopted at Community level with due regard to the development of validation within the OECD.

In relation to the tests concerning repeated-dose toxicity, reproductive toxicity and toxicokinetics, for which there are no alternatives yet under consideration, the period for implementation shall be limited to *11 March 2013*.

Level 1:
existing Data
non-test information

Level 2:
in vitro assays providing data about selected endocrine mechanism(s) / pathway(s)

Level 3:
in vivo assays providing data about selected endocrine mechanism(s) / pathway(s)

Level 4:
in vivo assays providing data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints

Level 5:
In vivo assays providing more comprehensive data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints over more extensive parts of the life cycle of the organism

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties
- available toxicological data (standardized or non-standardized tests)
- Read across, QSAR, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- Are the adverse effects potentially related to ED in intact organisms in acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD CF Level 4/5)?
- The available data provide convincing evidence or demonstrate an ED mode of action?
- Are the effects judged to be relevant to humans?

III. Prioritization

Decision matrix

- $\geq$ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED 1

SVHC identification (Article 57f)

- considered as to be of equivalent concern to CMR 1A/1B substances
Candidate for inclusion in REACH Annex XIV (Authorization)

ED 2

Standard Risk Assessment

- restrictions set according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

I. Data evaluation

Existing Data & non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties, available toxicological data from standardized or non-standardized tests, Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling
- ED-related *in-silico* predictions and a basic set of *in-vitro* assays addressing ED endpoint should be mandatory!**

II. Data analysis

Weight-of-evidence process

- acceptable *in-vitro* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 1/2)
- Read across, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME modelling, HBMOS concept, exposure
- acceptable *in-vivo* studies (e.g. OECD Conceptual Framework Level 4/5)**

Priorization impossible!

III. Priorization

Decision matrix

- ≥ guidance values STOT (Repeated Dose) Category 1 (CLP)
- severity of effect
- reversibility of effect
- others if applicable

Regulatory consequence(s)

ED effect suspected

Request for further toxicity testing

- Clarification of suspected ED related hazard would require animal testing
- Options:
Animal testing as an exception?
REACH substance evaluation?

No inclusion into Union list of

- Annex III (substances with restrictions)
- Annexes IV-VI (allowed substances)

Inclusion into

- Annex II (list of prohibited substances)

ED 1

Standard Risk Assessment

- restrictions set according to the most sensitive toxicological endpoint

ED 2

SUMMARY

1. In the interest of predictability, efficiency and consistency, the purpose of this concept is to ensure a high level of protection of human health under different regulations based on a scientific weighting of available data.
2. The decision tree combines a flexible scientific weight of evidence process and a conclusion based on an decision matrix including established toxicological guidance values (STOT RE Category 1 of CLP) which ensures
 - comprehensive decisions
 - assures predictability of legal decisions (e.g. in authorization procedures)
3. The concept was originally designed for substances where a complete set of toxicological data is available.

Yet, it provides a common principle for the evaluation and authorisation of ED substances to ensure a harmonised approach within different regulations:

- Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009
- Regulation (EC) No 528/2012
- Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH)
- Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 (Food additives)
- Regulation (EC) No 10/2011 (Plastic materials and articles intended to come into contacts with food)
- Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (Cosmetics).

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

UNDER PARTICIPATION OF...

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Endocrine disrupting chemicals

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OECD CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: TESTING AND ASSESSMENT OF EDCs (2011)

Level 1:
existing Data
non-test information

- Physical & chemical properties (e.g. MW, reactivity, volatility, biodegradability)
- Human & environmental exposure (e.g., production volume, release, use patterns)
- Hazard assessment (available (eco)toxicological data from standardized or non-standardized tests, read across, chemical categories, QSARs, other *in silico* predictions, ADME model predictions)

Level 2:
in vitro assays providing data about
selected endocrine mechanism(s) /
pathway(s)

- ER, AR, TR binding affinity
- Transcriptional activation (OECD TG 455 ER TTA; AR-, TR-TA when TGs available)
- Steroidogenesis *in vitro* (OECD TG 456)
- MCF-7 cell proliferation assays (ER ant/agonist)
- Other assays as appropriate (Aromatase, AhR receptor recognition/binding)

Level 3:
in vivo assays providing data about
selected endocrine mechanism(s) /
pathway(s)

Level 4:
in vivo assays providing data on adverse
effects on endocrine relevant endpoints

Level 5:
In vivo assays providing more
comprehensive data on adverse effects
on endocrine relevant endpoints over
more extensive parts of the life cycle of
the organism

OECD CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: TESTING AND ASSESSMENT OF EDCs (2011)

Level 3:

in vivo assays providing data about selected endocrine mechanism(s) / pathway(s)

Level 4:

in vivo assays providing data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints

Level 5:

In vivo assays providing more comprehensive data on adverse effects on endocrine relevant endpoints over more extensive parts of the life cycle of the organism

Mammalian toxicology:

- Uterotrophic assay (estrogenic related)
- Hershberger assay (androgenic related)
- Repeated dose 28d (TG 407)
- Repeated dose 90d (TG 408)
- 1-generation assay (TG 415)
- Male pubertal assay
- Female pubertal assay
- Intact adult male endocrine screening
- Prenatal developmental toxicity (TG414)
- Chronic toxicity & carcinogenicity (TG 451-3)
- Reproductive screening (TG 421 if enhanced)
- Combined 28d/reproductive screening (TG 422 if enhanced)
- Developmental neurotoxicity (TG 426)

- Extended one-generation reproductive Toxicity (TG 443)
- 2-Generation assay (TG 416 most recent update)

Non-mammalian toxicology:

- Xenopus embryo thyroid signalling assay*
- Amphibian metamorphosis (TG 231)
- Fish Reproductive Screening (TG 229)
- Fish Screening (TG 230)
- Androgenized female stickleback (GD 140)
- Fish sexual development (Draft TG 234)
- Fish Reproduction Partial Lifecycle Test*
- Larval Amphibian Growth & Development Assay*
- Avian Reproduction Assay (TG 206)
- Mollusc Partial Lifecycle Assays*
- Chironomid Toxicity Test (TG 218-219)
- Fish LifeCycle Toxicity Test*
- Medaka Multigeneration Test*
- Avian 2 generation reproductive toxicity*
- Mysid Life Cycle Toxicity Test*
- Copepod Reproduction & Development*
- Sediment Water Chironomid Life Cycle Toxicity Test (TG 233)
- Mollusc Full Lifecycle Assays*
- Daphnia Reproduction Test (TG 211)
- Daphnia Multigeneration Assay*

* when/if TG available